

Hormonal regulation involved in fat synthesis and fetal growth in humans and some species of zootechnical interest

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Abstract

Background and Objective: Peptide and lipid hormones play a fundamental role in fat metabolism and fetal growth in mammalian animals.

Methods: A narrative and opinion-based literature review was conducted, referencing the most recent publications (from the last 5 years), between January and April 2026. This involved planning and searching for verified scientific information published in indexed journals using search engines such as SciELO, Web of Science, Scopus, and Dialnet.

Results: Hormones composed of amino acids and fatty acids exert a pleiotrophic effect on the target organs (muscle and adipose tissue) of mammalian animals, being essential for the metabolism of myocytes and adipocytes.

Conclusions: Hormones are essential chemical substances for anabolic and catabolic regulation at the tissue level in animals and humans.

Keywords: Hormone; fat; protein; animal; fetus.

1. Introduction

Hormones are chemical substances of diverse molecular nature that, in small quantities, bind to plasma proteins via chemical signals to produce a specific effect on the target organ, which can be a tissue, specialized cells, or other structures. There are polypeptide and lipid hormones, both of which are essential for metabolic maintenance in animals and humans, from fertilization to death [1].

In this regard, studies have focused heavily on the role of hormones in final fat deposition and fetal development in animals and humans, as these periods are crucial in an individual's life. Hormones regulate internal homeostasis and anabolic and catabolic processes at the cellular level.

The objective of this article was to determine the Hormonal regulation involved in fat synthesis and fetal growth in humans and some species of zootechnical interest.

2. Methodology

A narrative and opinion-based literature review was conducted, referencing the most recent publications (from the last 5 years),

between January and April 2026. This involved planning and searching for verified scientific information published in indexed journals using search engines such as SciELO, Web of Science, Scopus, and Dialnet. The articles to be included in the manuscript were then filtered and selected, resulting in 21 articles that address the hormonal regulation involved in fat synthesis and fetal growth in humans and animals of zootechnical interest [2]. Subsequently, a theoretical and textual analysis of the findings from the scientific literature related to the topic was performed [3,4].

3. Development

3.1. Researchers discover genes that regulate saturated fat levels in cattle and humans

Recent work in metabolic genetics has discovered certain quantitative trait loci (QTL) that affect intramuscular fat synthesis in beef cattle meat, subcutaneous fat and its depth, as well as fat synthesis in bovine milk on chromosomes 6, 14, and 19 (Bos taurus autosomes: BTAs 6, 14, 19) [5].

A team of scientists identified the genes that regulate fat deposits in beef. Three single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) are related to fatty acid production in cattle. The scientists examined the relationship between genetic traits for high fatty acid content and fat deposition in the muscle of Angus bulls. SNPs occur when a single nucleotide in the genome sequence is altered. Many scientists believe that mapping SNPs may lead to the identification of multiple genes associated with animal productivity and meat fat composition [6].

These SNPs are the main keys to proteins expressed by genes containing these and other QTLs, and their physiological intervals in the regulation of intramuscular lipogenesis in muscle tissue and in cellular compartments and organelles of adipocytes in bovine species. Polymorphisms of the main candidate genes for lipogenic proteins are associated with an improvement in oleic acid and monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) in the longissimus muscle (LM) of animals of zootechnical interest [7].

On the other hand, an SNP in the genes that translate the anabolic enzymes “fatty acid synthase (FASN)” biochemically influences their transcription factor SP1-binding site, which is associated with variation in milk fat content. A recent study observed that an SNP in the thioesterase (TE) domain in the FASN gene was significantly associated with fatty acids in the LM composition of Angus bulls. Cattle with GG genotype specifications have been found to have lower SFA and higher oleic and MUFA fatty acid content in fatty acid concentration [8].

Recent genetic studies have also demonstrated associations between SNPs in bovine species and stearoyl coenzyme A desaturase (SCD) genes with higher MUFA content and lower LM melting point in adipose tissue of Japanese Black steers and with higher oleic acid content in total MUFA in dairy cows. Genetic analysis of SCD expression is essential for investigating polymorphisms in transcription factors such as sterols, which are regulatory elements linked to protein-1 (SREBP-1), and other genes related to lipids and fatty acid metabolism, providing a strong underlying functional cellular mechanism for the regulation of other lipogenic genes [9].

In addition, selective polymorphism in the SREBP-1 gene was positively associated with higher MUFA content in intramuscular fat in Japanese Black cattle. The crucial function of this gene is key to adipocyte synthesis and unsaturated fat deposition in cattle, indicating temporal differentiation and the induction of SREBP-1 and a peroxisome proliferator activated by gamma receptors (PPAR-gamma). Other studies have determined that fatty acid binding protein (FABP4), which is expressed in human adipose tissue, functionally interacts with peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPARs) and lipase-sensitive hormone, representing a strong candidate for genes involved in intramuscular fat in beef cattle and humans. FABP4 has even been linked to the pathology of systemic lupus erythematosus, which is an essential finding for the treatment of this

condition in human epithelial tissue and the influence that these fatty proteins have at the systemic level.

Other researchers have been particularly interested in a gene that codes for the protein known as “myostatin,” as it has an inhibitory effect on muscle cell growth in animals, including humans. But when the gene responsible (MSTN) for producing the protein is suppressed or altered in some way, the result is increased muscle growth and reduced fat deposition. Beef from cattle with two copies of the myostatin gene produces cuts with more meat and less fat than beef from cattle with no copies or one copy of the gene [10].

This demonstrates a protein and hormonal interaction that is now well understood, which translates into beneficial advances for animal and human health in terms of fatty acid metabolism. En la Figura 1, se muestra una infografía de la interacción de las moléculas antes mencionadas.

Fig 1. Molecular regulators of saturated fat in bovine and humans

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3.2. Hormonal regulation in fetal growth

Many hormones are involved in fetal development and growth. Both processes are extremely important in livestock production. The most notable distinction between fetal development and growth is the role played by the placenta as an organ of respiration, metabolism, and hormone production for the fetus. The placenta reaches its maximum size before the last third of gestation, when the greatest fetal growth occurs. However, it is also clear that the placenta has an important endocrine function [11].

In the debate about the endocrine function of the placenta, it is important to remember that amino acid-type hormones do not cross the placental membrane from the mother's blood to the fetal blood [12], even for a peptide as small as thyroxine. This differs markedly from steroid hormones, which, by virtue of their size and lipid solubility, can cross the placenta (or any membrane) with relative ease. This differs markedly from steroid hormones, which, by virtue of their size and lipid solubility, can cross the placenta (or any membrane) with relative ease. Therefore, the concentration of protein and lipid hormones in the mother and fetus must be considered individually. A hormone synthesized in the placenta can go in either direction (maternal or fetal) depending on the hormone and the species considered.

Other trials support the hypothesis that GH is not as relevant in regulating fetal growth, as demonstrated by studies with sheep and pigs. Several studies have observed a significant negative correlation between plasma GH concentration and birth weight in lambs [13]. Almeida and Alvarenga [14] observed differences in fetal weight at 90 and 100 days of gestation between obese pigs, but no differences in plasma GH concentration. These data suggest that GH is not important for the normal development of the species mentioned.

Likewise, prolactin has a marked relationship with hyperplasia and hypertrophy of fetal cells in animals and humans. A positive relationship between prolactin concentration and birth weight in children is fundamental [15]. Prolactin concentration in sheep plasma delayed fetal growth when it was less than 5% compared to normal human fetuses [16]. In contrast to GH, prolactin binding to the fetal liver membrane in sheep is as high as it is in adult animals. One report has indicated that prolactin is more potent than GH in eliciting somatotropin release by the rat liver [17]. Prolactin decreases the diffusion of water from the mother to the fetus through the human placenta and alters cell movement and active transport through the porcine placenta.

On the other hand, relatively little is known about the role of thyroid hormones in development. Osorio and Uribe [18] observed decreased body weight, wool development, and impaired bone ossification after removal of the thyroid glands of fetal sheep. In contrast, thyroidectomy in rabbit fetuses does not affect fetal weight gain, although body fat increased [19].

Along the same lines, we have another hormone of great importance, “progesterone,” which, apart from maintaining pregnancy, plays a clear quantitative role in fetal development. There is considerable absorption of progesterone by pigs and cattle [20], and it is used in the uterus for the synthesis of androgens or estrogens by the fetus. In contrast, the ovine placenta is the main source of progesterone in the second half of gestation [21]. Consequently, increases in maternal progesterone concentration are observed with the progressive development of gestation. Therefore, it could be expected that the absorption of progesterone by the uterine content correlates with fetal size.

Insulin has also been considered a fetal growth hormone, and there is scientific literature supporting the relationship between insulin and fetal development in humans and laboratory animals. Human babies born to diabetic mothers tend to be heavier [22] than babies born to non-diabetic mothers. Similarly, Tim [23] observed that fetuses of rats injected with insulin at 17, 18, and 19 days of gestation had significantly higher body weight, as well as higher lipid and N levels, compared to control fetuses. In addition, Almeida and Alvarenga [14] observed that a higher concentration of insulin in the blood of young sows (and their fetuses) increased crude protein (CP) intake from the diet by 18%. They also reported a high fetal correlation between insulin concentration and fetal growth rate [24]. Figure 2 illustrates the points explained in the previous paragraphs.

Fig 2. Hormonal regulation of fetal growth in animals of zootechnical interest and humans

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4. Conclusions

Each of the hormones analyzed in this article has a specific function, but in synergy they have antagonistic effects, depending on the gestational period of the animal in relation to fetal development. It is important to continue conducting trials to determine more specific physiological effects in animals and humans.

References

- Rivas López PC, Suárez Londoño Á, Ramírez Cardona E. Influencia de las hormonas metabólicas y la nutrición en el desarrollo folicular en el ganado bovino: implicaciones prácticas. *Rev Med Vet.* 2011; (21): 155-173.
- Corona J, Kovac M. Perspectiva epistemológica empírico-positivista y fenomenológica-hermenéutica: significado, objeto de estudio y aplicabilidad. *Novo Tékhné.* 2016; 2(2): 89-97.

3. Corona J, Maldonado J. Qualitative Research: Emic-Etic Approach. *Rev Cubana Invest Bioméd.* 2018; 37(4): 1-4.
4. Corona J. Qualitative research: Epistemological, theoretical and methodological foundations. *Vivat Academia.* 2018; (144): 69-76.
5. Camargo Pitalua CA, Montes Vergara DE, Pérez Cordero A. Marcadores moleculares y genes asociados a calidad de carne en el ganado bovino. *Rev Colomb Cienc Anim Recia.* 2024; 16(1): e07.
6. Vesga DA, Salcedo YT. Suplementación lipídica para la producción de carne bovina en confinamientos. *Rev Colomb Cienc Anim Recia.* 2021; 13(2): 62-71.
7. Bergamaschi M, Tiezzi F, Howard J, et al. Las diferencias en la composición del microbioma intestinal entre razas afectan la eficiencia alimentaria en cerdos. *Microbiome.* 2020; 8: 110.
8. Ramírez E. Perfiles de los ácidos grasos y sus modificaciones en la calidad de la carne de los bovinos. *Agro Productividad.* 2018; 10(10).
9. Soria LA, Corva PM. Factores genéticos y ambientales que determinan la terneza de la carne bovina. *Arch Latinoam Prod Anim.* 2004; 12(2).
10. IVAMI. Hipertrofia muscular relacionada con la miostatina. *IVAMI.* 2020.
11. Prats C, Berveiller P. Fisiología del crecimiento fetal. *Ginecol Obstet.* 2023; 59(1): 1-11.
12. Page L, Younge N, Freemark M. Hormonal determinants of growth and weight gain in the human fetus and preterm infant. *Nutrients.* 2023; 15(18): 4041.
13. Álvarez A. Señales embrionarias y hormonas placentarias: bases moleculares y potencial uso para el diagnóstico y el seguimiento de la gestación en animales de interés productivo. *Arch Latinoam Prod Anim.* 2023; 30(3).
14. Almeida F, Alvarenga A. Embarazo en cerdos: el viaje de una vida temprana. *Domest Anim Endocrinol.* 2022; (78): 106656.
15. Bartlewski PM, Baby TE, Giffin JL. Reproductive cycles in sheep. *Anim Reprod Sci.* 2011; 124(3-4): 259-268.
16. Gómez T, García M, Bequer L, et al. Malformaciones esqueléticas y alteraciones del crecimiento en fetos de ratas con diabetes moderada. *Biomédica.* 2021; 41(3): 493-503.
17. Feng P, Wu J, Ren Y, et al. El embarazo temprano regula la expresión de prolactina y su receptor en el timo, el hígado, el bazo y los ganglios linfáticos de las ovejas. *Domest Anim Endocrinol.* 2022; 81: 106731.
18. Osorio JH, Suárez YJ, Uribe LF. Hormonas tiroideas en pequeños rumiantes: artículo de revisión y actualización de la literatura. *Biosalud.* 2014; 13(1): 85-95.
19. Falla-Zúñiga LF, Sinner D, Moreno-Martínez D, et al. *Mus musculus*: biomodelo de expresión de Desyodinasas (DIO3) y Transtiretina (TTR) en el desarrollo placentario. *Entramado.* 2021; 17(1): 218-230.
20. Narváez HJ, da Silva Fontes R, Campos de Carvalho B, et al. Efecto de la progesterona plasmática en la competencia para el desarrollo embrionario in vitro de vacas *Bos taurus taurus* y *Bos taurus indicus*. *Cienc Tecnol Agropecuaria.* 2022; 23(2): e2003.
21. Lonergan P, Sánchez J. Revisión del simposio: efectos de la progesterona en el desarrollo embrionario temprano en el ganado. *J Dairy Sci.* 2020; 103(9): 8698-8707.
22. Ormeño-Julca AJ. Interacciones entre los genes y el medio ambiente en la obesidad infantil. *Rev Cubana Pediatr.* 2022; 94(2).
23. Huijsmans TERG, Van Soom A, Smits K, et al. Review: The role of prolactin in the maternal investment-survival balance. *Theriogenology Wild.* 2023; (5): 100109.
24. Corona J. Causas genéticas relacionadas con anomalías en la diferenciación sexual en animales mamíferos. *Rev Cubana Invest Bioméd.* 2015; 34(4): 378-383.

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